

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Choose Your Moments: NIH Peer Review and Scientific Risk Taking"

**James M. Zumel Dumlao¹ B. Ian Hutchins² David Reinstein
Joshua Graff Zivin³**

¹PhD Candidate at the University of Michigan School of Information,

²University of Wisconsin-Madison, ³University of California San Diego

Published on: Jun 01, 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21428/d28e8e57.df86328a>

License: [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC-BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "Choose Your Moments: NIH Peer Review and Scientific Risk Taking"^[1]. The evaluators identify the paper's claim that "scientists have a preference for 'dissensus' among reviewers' scores" and are largely convinced by this. However, the first evaluator (Dumlao) is less confident in the claim that "higher score variance is correlated with higher-risk research with greater potential to have positive impacts for the public." The evaluations are positive overall, praising many aspects of the paper's design ("the balanced incomplete block design approach is well-suited to the ... internal NIH data"). Their ratings suggest the paper merits publication in a "top B-journal", a "marginal A-Journal" and possibly a "top journal". Both evaluators suggest ways to make the paper more credible and useful (e.g., inter-rater reliability as a robustness check). The second evaluator (Hutchins) provides particular contextual insights ("the assertion that grants can be resubmitted twice is out of date") and suggestions to improve communication and impact ("asterisks denoting ... $p < 0.10$ will ... reduce confidence by biomedical audiences, including at NIH").

Evaluations

1. [James Dumlao](#)
2. [B. Ian Hutchins](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote¹)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in?² *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
James Dumlao	70	3.8
B. Ian Hutchins	75	4.0

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

James Dumlao

This paper includes two experiments aimed at informing reform in the NIH grant peer review process. The first experiment finds that biomedical scientists have a preference for studies with higher score variance (“dissensus”), interpreted as a desire for risk-taking. The second experiment finds that tightening budgets reduces scientists’ dissensus tolerance. Authors conclude that relaxed budgets and rewarding dissensus would encourage the production of more high-impact science.

B. Ian Hutchins

“Choose Your Moments: NIH Peer Review and Scientific Risk Taking” is an interesting study on review decision-making. Authors examine the effect of NIH peer review score distribution on decision-making about funding particular grants, using a portfolio from NIH 2016 RePORTER data, using a BIBD approach. Their approach is sound and I am persuaded by their conclusion that reviewers have a preference for grants with increased variance in review scores, and that there is an asymmetry in preference for high-variance applications in response to funding shocks.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1			Evaluator 2		
	James Dumlao			B. Ian Hutchins		
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments
Overall assessment ⁴	70	(50, 90)		75	(60, 80)	
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁵	56	(45, 61)	6	75	(60, 80)	

Advancing knowledge and practice ⁷	72	(66, 84)	8	80	(75, 90)	
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁹	76	(68, 85)	10	60	(50, 70)	
Logic & communication 11	55	(45, 70)	12	45	(35, 55)	13
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹⁴	65	(50, 79)	15	30	(15, 45)	16
Real-world relevance 17, 18	50	(40, 60)	19	80	(75, 89)	
Relevance to global priorities ^{20, 21}	50	(40, 60)		80	(75, 89)	

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1 James Dumlao		Evaluator 2 B. Ian Hutchins	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	3.8	(3.0, 4.1)	4.0	(2.5, 4.5)

What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	3.9	(3.5, 4.3)	3.5	(2.5, 4.0)
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 			

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	Main research claim ²²	Belief in claim ²³	Suggested robustness checks ²⁴	Important 'implication', policy, credibility ²⁵
Evaluator 1 James Dumlao	<p>Claim 1: Scientists have a preference for "dissensus" among reviewers' scores.</p> <p>Claim 2: Higher score variance is correlated with higher risk research with greater potential to have positive impacts for the public.</p>	<p>Claim 1: 95% true</p> <p>Claim 2: Much less tenable, 65% true (lacks direct evidence from the studies conducted)</p>	N/A	N/A

Evaluator 2 B. Ian Hutchins	Reviewers have a preference for grants with increased variance in review scores, and ... there is an asymmetry in preference for high-variance applications in response to funding shocks in the positive vs. negative direction.	I am persuaded unless I see contrary evidence. I have seen primary internal NIH data, and this comports with that experience.	Inter-rater reliability information, if available.	Program Officers should be provided with summary statistics about review variance.
---------------------------------------	---	---	--	--

Authors' brief response

Joshua Graff Zivin provided the following response:

We are grateful for the thoughtful and constructive feedback provided by both reviewers. In response, we will strengthen our discussion of higher moments by engaging more deeply with the existing literature, while acknowledging that our current hypothetical setting does not allow us to empirically evaluate these effects. As noted in the manuscript, the true relationship between higher moments and grant outcomes can only be estimated with historical data from the NIH or other grant-making agencies. We remain hopeful that this will someday become available to researchers. We also appreciate Reviewer 1's suggestion to explore heterogeneity across dimensions of the score—such as team quality or innovativeness—which we view as a compelling direction for future experimental work, though not one we can pursue within the current design.²⁶

Reviewer 2's comments were particularly helpful in encouraging us to clarify the policy relevance of our findings and better frame the study for a broader, interdisciplinary audience. We also agree with Reviewer 2 that further exploration of inter-rater reliability would be valuable, and we will examine whether our data are sufficiently powered to support such an analysis, despite the limitations of our current design.

Unjournal process notes

Why we chose this paper

From our internal discussion:

It's one of the few papers trying to understand grant design and how that impacts science.

Seems to be targeting a high-value question: using grant design (amount, timing) to motivate risk-taking in scientific research. It's based on a hypothetical survey/thought experiment, but this is probably the best approach to a challenging question...

References

1. Carson, R. T., Graff Zivin, J. S., & Shrader, J. G. (2023). Choose Your Moments: Peer Review and Scientific Risk Taking. NBER Working Paper No. 31409. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w31409>

Footnotes

1. We asked them to rank this paper "heuristically" as a percentile "relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years." We requested they "consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. [↵](#)
2. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↵](#)
3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)
4. Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↵](#)

5. "Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?"

This was on the newer form only [↵](#)

6. Some overclaiming in connecting findings to policy recommendations. [↵](#)
- 7.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↵](#)

8. Studies advance knowledge well, but findings lack direct connection to policy. [↵](#)

9. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↵](#)

10. Experimental methods and robustness checks make for high internal validity. [↵](#)

11. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↵](#)

12. Major logical leap from score variance to risk tolerance to high-impact science not well-motivated. Otherwise, writing style is very accessible and clear. [↵](#)

13. More details on randomization would be much appreciated. [↵](#)

14.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

[↵](#)

15. Procedures clearly states, experiment conditions/instruments provided, no data shared. [↵](#)

16. As far as I can tell, there is no open data or code, which is becoming the norm. [↵](#)

17.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

[↵](#)

18.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

19. Variance could be useful for breaking ties, but not clear that it is *the* information to incorporate into funding decisions over other forms of information. More information is likely always beneficial, some comparison to other possible policy interventions would make relevance more apparent. ↵

20. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? ↵

21.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" ↵

22.

The evaluator was given the following instructions:

Identify the most important and impactful factual claim this research makes – e.g., a binary claim or a point estimate or prediction.

Please state the authors' claim precisely and quantitatively. Identify the source of the claim (i.e., cite the paper), and briefly mention the evidence underlying this. We encourage you to explain why you believe this claim is important, either here, or in the text of your report. ↵

23. Evaluators were asked: To what extent do you **believe** the claim you stated above? Feel free to express this either a. in terms of the probability of the claim being true, b. as a credible interval for the parameter being estimated, or c. however you feel comfortable. ↵

24.

We asked:

[Optional] What additional information, evidence, replication, or robustness check would make you substantially more (or less) confident in this claim?

Feel free to refer to the main body of your evaluation here; you don't need to repeat yourself. Please specify how you would perform this robustness check (etc.) as precisely as you are willing. E.g., if you suggest a particular estimation command in a statistical package, this could be very helpful for future robustness replication work. ↵

25.

We asked:

[Optional] Identify the important **implication** of the above claim for funding and policy choices? To what extent do you **believe** this implication? How should it inform policy choices?

Note: this 'implication' could be suggested by the evaluation manager in some cases. As an example of an 'implication' ... in a global health context, the 'main claim' might suggest that a vitamin supplement intervention, if scaled up, would save lives at a \$XXXXX per life saved.

We did not ask this in the 'applied stream' as it is most likely redundant.

↵

26. Manager: paragraph break added

↵

References

1. Carson, R., Zivin, J. S. G., & Shrader, J. (2023). *Choose Your Moments: Peer Review and Scientific Risk Taking*. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w31409> ↵